

Natural and targeted circuit reorganization after spinal cord injury

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Abstract

A spinal cord injury (SCI) disrupts the communication between the brain and the circuits in the spinal cord that regulate neurological functions. The consequences are permanent paralysis, loss of sensation, and debilitating dysautonomia. However, the majority of circuits located above and below the injury remain anatomically intact. Therefore, these circuits can reorganize naturally to improve function. Various neuromodulation therapies have tapped into these circuits to further augment recovery. Moreover, we are beginning to map the requirements to reconstitute damaged circuits. Here, we summarize these natural and targeted reorganizations of circuits after SCI. We also advocate the need for new concepts of reorganizing circuits informed by multi-omic single-cell atlases of recovery from injury. These atlases will uncover the molecular logic governing the selection of *recovery-organizing* neuronal subpopulations, heralding a new era in spinal cord medicine.

Introduction

The circuits that regulate motor and autonomic functions reside in the spinal cord. While these circuits are often regarded as rudimentary components of the nervous system under the authoritative control of the brain and brainstem, we are beginning to uncover a remarkable sophistication and diversity in the molecular architecture of the neuronal subpopulations that forge these circuits^{1,2}. Equally refined is the organization of the brain and brainstem regions that interact with neurons in the spinal cord. Interrogation of neuronal subpopulations based on their identity and/or projection targets have revealed that these regions can no longer be schematized with interacting boxes delivering executive commands to the spinal cord through specialized descending pathways³. Instead, each region is composed of specific neuronal subpopulations with distinct receptomes and projectomes that contribute uniquely to the production of behavior⁴. Deciphering the logic of neuronal subpopulations across the nervous system and how they interact to regulate motor and autonomic functions is a daunting task. Even more intimidating is the attempt to understand how these neuronal subpopulations respond to, and reorganize after, an SCI.

Until recently, probing the functional role of neuronal subpopulations has been a laborious and low-throughput endeavor. Therefore, our knowledge on the reorganization of circuits after SCI primarily derived from the interrogation of broadly defined pathways and circuits that are thought to be important in the regulation of motor and autonomic functions.

Here, we summarize our knowledge on how the circuits located in the brain, brainstem and spinal cord respond to SCI, and how their reorganization can not only contribute to natural recovery but also to degradation of neurological functions, **both in animal models and in humans. We primarily focus on motor functions, but also evoke autonomic functions when relevant.** We discuss how neuromodulation technologies can engage and reorganize the intact neuronal subpopulations above and below an SCI to improve these functions. We then lay out our understanding of the requirements to reconstitute damaged circuits. Finally, we discuss the importance of shifting away from the study of vaguely defined pathways, circuits, or regions. Instead, we must increase the resolution of our nervous system interrogation by uncovering the properties and roles of *recovery-organizing* neurons—**the specific neuronal subpopulations that contribute to promoting anatomical reorganization or restoring function after SCI**—and how they can be targeted to **further improve spinal cord repair and functional recovery.**

Adaptive and maladaptive reorganization of circuits following SCI

An SCI induces the death of **neurons and glia in and around spinal cord lesions, and the interruption of axons passing through this region.** However, the impact of SCI is not restricted to the mechanical disruption of tissues in the region of insult. Circuits located far away from the injury, both above and below the SCI, undergo profound changes that can contribute to natural recovery^{5,6} or instead be detrimental^{7,8}. Indeed, local growth of residual descending fibers, sprouting of synaptic terminals, adaptations in synaptic transmission, and multifaceted changes in molecular properties of neurons have been documented in numerous regions of the brain, brainstem, and spinal cord. The degree and nature of these adaptive and maladaptive modifications primarily depends on the severity of SCI, as we summarize below (**Fig. 1**).

Reorganization of brain circuits

The majority of studies that investigated the contribution of the brain to recovery after SCI focused on the cerebral cortex. Why? Neuronal populations embedded in the cerebral cortex are essential for hand dexterity, are the most experimentally accessible neurons, and determine the advanced motor skills of primate species. Indeed, classical experiments in nonhuman primate (NHP) models revealed that dexterous movements are not possible when corticospinal tract projections are interrupted⁹. Accordingly, the integrity of the corticospinal tract is a key predictor of natural **functional** recovery after SCI **in humans**¹⁰.

One of the most striking mechanisms of recovery uncovered by these studies involves time-dependent, bilateral reorganization of cortical dynamics. This mechanism has been described after lateralized SCI in NHP models¹¹. Concretely, the activity of the motor and sensory cortex from both hemispheres was found to be increased early after SCI. Once recovery had taken place, however, the increased activity was restricted to the contralesional motor and sensory cortex and to both ventral premotor cortices. **Silencing experiments confirmed that ipsilesional cortical regions are necessary for movement execution, but only during the early phase after the SCI**¹¹. **Functional remapping of cortical regions during recovery from SCI in rodents also illustrated the importance of time-dependent changes in cortical dynamics**^{12,13}. **When cortically-derived projections in the spinal cord below injury were silenced, the recovery of movement vanished immediately, showing the relevance of this reorganization to regain function after SCI**^{5,14}.

Anatomical reorganization of cortically-derived projections¹⁵ and ascending pathways¹⁶ parallels these adaptations of cortical dynamics. When the SCI spares a subset of fibers from the corticospinal tract, these fibers undergo a directed growth to invade the gray matter territories deprived of brain and brainstem projections^{17,18}. This targeted growth can occur over several millimeters. After a lateral hemisection SCI, for example, corticospinal tract fibers can branch from the contralesional dorsolateral column, cross the spinal cord midline, and develop dense synaptic projections into the ventral gray matter where they contact neuronal subpopulations involved in the control of hand function¹⁹. Interventions that enhance this growth further augment hand function recovery²⁰. Although the mechanisms triggering this process remain unclear, regression of corticospinal tract neurons to a transcriptional state similar to developing neurons appears responsible for enabling this growth²¹. The reorganization of cortically-derived projections has been exposed in rodent and NHP models, but evidence suggests that this mechanism also supports natural functional recovery in humans²².

When the SCI interrupts all corticospinal tract projections, the executive commands from the motor cortex can also be rerouted through alternative pathways with surviving projections below the injury (**Fig. 1**). For example, the growth of cortically-derived projections onto neurons located in the reticular formation enables the recovery of walking after contusion SCI⁵. Due to the ubiquitous location of reticulospinal fibers within the rim of spinal cord white matter, a subset of these fibers survive contusion SCI, regardless of the inherently variable topology of damage⁵. Similarly, sprouting of cortically-derived projections within the red nucleus enables the motor cortex to convey sufficient information to the spinal cord through the rubrospinal tract to regain meaningful upper limb function^{23–26}. The formation of relays through reticulospinal and rubrospinal neurons underscores the important role of brainstem-derived projections²⁷, and suggests the existence of *recovery-organizing* neurons located in distributed regions of the brainstem.

Reorganization of brainstem circuits

A century of research has documented the parcellation of brainstem architecture. Accordingly, we know that highly-specialized descending pathways project from specific regions of the brainstem to the spinal cord where they contact interneurons or motor neurons involved in the regulation of motor and autonomic functions. This knowledge has informed targeted studies that investigated the impact of SCI on these pathways, and their putative role during recovery.

Multiple investigations documented the growth of reticulospinal⁵, rubrospinal²⁸ and serotonergic²⁹ projections within territories located below various types and severities of SCI (**Fig. 1**). This growth often recapitulates the natural innervation pattern of these projections^{5,30}, suggesting an attempt to re-establish the normal connectivity of these pathways. Electrophysiological, lesion and projection-specific silencing experiments have linked this anatomical remodeling with recovery^{5,29}.

However, the involvement of subcortical structures cannot be restricted to pathways projecting directly to the spinal cord. One striking example is the necessary contribution of the nucleus accumbens to the execution of dexterous hand movements, especially early after SCI³¹. Another unexpected contribution of evolutionary ancient subcortical regions comes from the mesencephalic locomotor region (MLR)³². While this region is not necessary to produce walking in the absence of injury³³, neurons distributed within the MLR are capable of recruiting reticulospinal neurons with surviving projections to produce locomotion after SCI³⁴.

Limiting the survey of *recovery-organizing* brainstem neurons to regions with residual projections below the SCI also fails to acknowledge the diversity of circuits within and across brainstem regions. For example, the MLR contains distinct subpopulations of glutamatergic neurons that project to specific targets in order to regulate distinct behaviors³⁵. It is also well established that reticulospinal neurons cluster in spatially defined regions depending on their contribution to the control of specific limbs³⁶ or unique behaviors³⁷. Moreover, projection-stratified neuronal subpopulations of the brainstem encode discrete actions and phases of actions, and they may even serve as building blocks for regulating complex movements³⁸.

This stratification of brainstem neuronal subpopulations in interactive, hierarchically-organized layers suggest that multiple regions may interact to pass executive commands downstream. Therefore, natural recovery from SCI may involve multifaceted changes in the flow of communication amongst multiple yet specific subcortical neuronal populations. Concomitant adaptations in the receptome and projectome of these *recovery-organizing* neuronal subpopulations likely take place to support recovery, but this remodeling has not been documented.

These observations reveal that functional recovery after SCI may rely on unexpected circuit reorganization, including the recruitment of evolutionarily conserved mechanisms that are not essential to produce behaviors in the absence of injury, but that become essential to support recovery after SCI. The critical role of mesolimbic and mesencephalic regions are perfect illustrations of this mechanism, but similar examples have also been described in the spinal cord.

Reorganization of spinal circuits above the injury

The studies described above leave no doubt that the motor cortex is essential to regain motor functions after SCI, **especially in primates**. Yet, equally certain is that cortical commands do not have to be transferred directly to the spinal cord below the injury to restore walking or even some degree of dexterous hand movements. A remarkable example comes from the ability of propriospinal neurons located in C3-C4 segments to relay cortical signals past a SCI to restore hand dexterity in NHP models³⁹. Importantly, these evolutionarily conserved neurons are not critical in the absence of injury, but they become essential to recover hand functions when direct corticospinal tract projections are interrupted (**Fig. 1**).

The same mechanism supports recovery of walking after dorsal or lateral hemisection SCI¹³, and even temporally and spatially separated hemisection SCI. In this scenario, all the direct pathways from the brain are interrupted as a result of the two opposite side hemisections. Yet, the neurons located between the hemisections can form relays that transfer sufficient information past the injury to restore basic leg movements^{18,40,41}. Again, although these neurons are not necessary to walk before the SCI¹³, they become essential after the SCI. Many of the neurons and descending propriospinal projections forming these relays are preserved after simultaneous hemisections. However, injury-mediated downregulation of the potassium-chloride cotransporter KCC2 in inhibitory neurons located in-between the hemisections leads to excessive inhibition of relay circuits, rendering them nonfunctional⁴⁰. Experimental prevention of KCC2 downregulation maintains the balance between inhibition and excitation, which is sufficient to restore basic walking⁴⁰.

These experiments revealed that after an incomplete SCI, spinal cord neurons above the injury can become *recovery-organizing* cells that relay commands from the brain and brainstem to reestablish motor functions. However, the molecular identity of these neurons and computational principles enabling these cells to transfer meaningful information to reorganizing circuits below the injury will require investigations with higher resolution.

Directed reorganization of spinal circuits below the injury

The interruption of brain- and brainstem-derived projections triggers a dramatic reorganization of spinal circuits located below the injury. **When residual supraspinal projections are abundant, these surveying fibers extend collaterals onto reorganizing circuits below the injury, which supports functional recovery^{5,19,27}. Neurorehabilitation can also direct the reorganization of spinal circuits below the injury to mediate adaptive changes that improve recovery, even following complete SCI^{42,43}.** When deprived of sufficient guidance, however, spinal circuits undergo a maladaptive reorganization that provokes detrimental clinical syndromes. In the next sections, we summarize our knowledge on **directed (adaptive) and undirected (maladaptive)** reorganization of spinal circuits below the injury (**Fig. 1**).

A century of research in physiology has demonstrated that spinal circuits can produce complex motor behaviors in the absence of any influence from the brain and brainstem^{44,45}. Central to this competence is the ability of spinal circuits to transform task-specific sensory information into patterns of muscle activity that meet the intrinsic biomechanical constraints and extrinsic environmental demands⁴⁶. These properties entail that feedback circuits are key components of the spinal circuits that produce motor behaviors. The implications for recovery after SCI are manifold. When supraspinal projections are compromised, sensory information must become the main source of control for movement⁴⁷. **Indeed, limb immobilization alters functional recovery after SCI⁴⁸. Instead, neurorehabilitation can direct activity-dependent functional⁴⁹ and anatomical⁵⁰**

reorganization of sensory projections that augments the transmission along feedback circuits and supports recovery. A logical consequence is the necessity of feedback circuits to execute and regain motor functions⁵¹, especially those originating from muscle proprioceptive organs⁵¹. Indeed, the genetic ablation of muscle spindle feedback circuits abolishes the recovery that naturally occurs after incomplete SCI. Concomitantly, brainstem and spinal cord relay neurons fail to respond to injury with the growth of new projections that normally mediates this recovery⁶. These observations contribute to explaining why the outcome of neurorehabilitation depends so singularly on the coincidence between the flow of sensory information and the volitional drive from residual supraspinal projections. However, the nature and topology of the interactions that promote this growth remain unknown. **It is also unclear how the spinal cord compensates for the interruption of monoamines that widens the receptive fields of motoneurons to proprioceptive afferents after SCI⁵².** Yet, there is mounting evidence that proprioceptive neurons are *recovery-organizing* cells that steer beneficial reorganization of circuits throughout the nervous system. Moreover, improving chromatin accessibility of proprioceptive neurons after SCI endows their axons with increased regenerative capacities, which can contribute to augmenting recovery⁵³.

The impact of SCI on neuronal functions is profound. Accordingly, it is difficult to identify sublesional cells that are not perturbed when a severe spinal cord damage occurs. Yet, functional recovery is likely to rely more prominently on the reorganization of specific neuronal subpopulations^{54,55}. For example, the recruitment of developmentally-defined V2a neurons during the recovery of walking¹ and breathing⁵⁶ suggests that these cells modify how they interact with the circuits that produce these functions. Neurons located in spinal cord deep layers (dl3) have also been implicated⁵⁷. Suppressing the synaptic transmission of these neurons does not impair walking but prevents recovery, suggesting that these cells broadcast reorganizing information within spinal circuits.

These observations stress the importance of shifting the focus on clearly-defined neuronal subpopulations. Single-cell technologies have now exposed a remarkable diversity of neuronal subpopulations in the spinal cord. Original nomenclatures were derived from the known cardinal lineages in both the developing and postnatal spinal cord^{1,58}. More recently, a top-down approach identified orderly genetic tiers that divide neuronal subpopulations according to their motor-sensory, local-long range, and excitatory-inhibitory features². We anticipate that this developmentally-driven taxonomy will rapidly lead to a harmonized catalog of neuronal subpopulations in the developing and adult spinal cord⁵⁹. **Although identifying truly homogenous populations of neurons may be a challenge during the development of these catalogs, rapidly advancing tools will enable their genetic accessibility through boolean logic.** These tools will enable the rapid identification of the most relevant, *recovery-organizing* neurons in the spinal cord after SCI.

Undirected reorganization of spinal circuits below the injury

The massive depletion of supraspinal projections induces a florilege of maladaptive compensatory responses that are responsible for various clinical syndromes (**Fig. 1**).

When a region of the central nervous system is deafferented, new synapses derived from unaffected afferent pathways form spontaneously⁶⁰. After SCI, this compensatory homeostatic response⁶¹ contributes to the aberrant sprouting of afferents from large-diameter and nociceptive dorsal root ganglia neurons^{7,62}, the chaotic growth of new propriospinal connections⁶³, and the ubiquitous genesis of excitatory synapses throughout the spinal cord below the injury^{7,64}. **Moreover,**

the disruption of blood flow below the injury leads to a chronic state of hypoxia owing to paradoxical excess activity of monoamine receptors on pericytes, which impairs neuronal function⁶⁵. Parallel changes in the molecular properties of spinal neurons take place. These include an increase in constitutive activity of monoaminergic receptors⁶⁶, serotonin hypersensitivity⁶⁷, upregulation of intracellular chloride concentration⁶⁸, increased excitability of various classes of neurons⁶⁹, and hyperactivity of L-type calcium channels⁷⁰.

Unlike the directed reorganization occurring when sufficient supraspinal projections persist, this undirected formation of circuits after severe SCI leads to clinical syndromes, including abnormal proprioceptive reflex responses^{7,71}, increased muscle tone⁷², spontaneous spasms⁷, bladder overactivity⁷³, neuropathic pain⁷⁴, and autonomic dysreflexia⁷⁵.

Various types of interneurons and circuits have been incriminated in these clinical syndromes⁷⁶. Indeed, the challenge may be to identify a neuronal subpopulation that does not undergo changes following a severe SCI. Yet, we surmise that this chaos involves the recruitment of specific neuronal subpopulations whose individual responses are directed towards predictable targets. Genetic tools are becoming available to manipulate these neuronal subpopulations in order to augment recovery.

Perspectives on natural circuit reorganization

This unstructured registry of pathways, regions and circuits that may contribute to various extents to the recovery or deterioration of neurological functions underscores the incompleteness of our knowledge. Moreover, observations that recovery may rely on unexpected mechanisms or regions not critical to neurological functions in the absence of injury leaves the possibility that critically important *recovery-organizing* regions and/or neuronal subpopulations may have been overlooked by previous studies that were merely informed by fundamental principles uncovered in uninjured animal models.

The identification of *recovery-organizing* neuronal subpopulations is contingent on catalogs of genetically-accessible neurons. These catalogs are now available for most brain regions⁷⁷, but the brainstem and spinal cord have comparatively remained less explored. Consequently, previous studies were forced to rely on developmentally-defined neuronal subtypes **or broadly defined neuronal subtypes**, which may or may not reflect the diversity of neuronal subpopulations in the adult nervous system^{1,2,78}. However, current technologies are now enabling us to generate spatially-resolved catalogs of neuronal subpopulations in high-throughput⁷⁹, auguring the imminent availability of comprehensive atlases over the entire nervous system. **Moreover, the statistical methods to navigate the uncharted landscape of nervous system territories are expanding quickly**^{1,80}.

Understanding the specific *recovery-organizing* neuronal subpopulations in the brain, brainstem, and spinal cord that contribute to the natural recovery of function after incomplete SCI is essential, since this knowledge can be harnessed to develop neuromodulation and biological repair therapies that target these neurons to augment recovery after more severe SCI, as we discuss in the next sections.

Neuromodulation of anatomically intact circuits

Spinal cord damage disrupts the flow of communication between the circuits that regulate motor and autonomic functions, but spares the vast majority of neurons that compose them. Consequently, various neuromodulation strategies **primarily based on electricity** have tapped into anatomically intact neurons and circuits of the brain, brainstem, and spinal cord to improve neurological functions after SCI (**Fig. 2**).

Neuromodulation of cortical circuits

Cortical circuits exert hierarchical control over brainstem and spinal circuits involved in the production of movement. Therefore, targeting cortical circuits provides broad access to a multitude of circuits located downstream. A perfect example of this hierarchical organization is illustrated in the immediate recovery of walking when stimulating the motor cortex after a lateral hemisection⁸¹. Despite the interruption of corticospinal tract projections on one side, adjusting the amplitude of intracortical stimulation patterns in closed-loop was sufficient to control the amplitude of stepping movements from the paralyzed leg on the denervated side⁸¹. The same observations were obtained during graded optogenetic activation of cortical projection neurons after contusion SCI⁵. Since this injury abolished all corticospinal projections, the optogenetically-evoked signals were relayed through glutamatergic reticulospinal neurons that retained projections below the SCI. These results indicate that the broad activation of cortical circuits can propagate commands that cascade downstream through brainstem neurons with spared yet functionally silent projections below the SCI.

Activity-dependent stimulation protocols can also strengthen the residual connections between the brain and spinal cord (**Fig. 2**). The underlying molecular mechanisms remain unclear, but it is now established that the repeated activation of the motor cortex with noninvasive or invasive electrical stimulation methods promotes activity-dependent growth of corticospinal tract projections⁸². Pairing motor cortex stimulation with precisely-timed recruitment of peripheral nerves or even intraspinal stimulation further enhances the transmission along residual neural pathways⁸³. The resulting spike-timing-dependent reorganization of circuits has mediated lasting improvement of motor functions and reduced spasticity in animal models⁸⁴ and people with SCI⁸⁵.

Neuromodulation of cortical circuits can also be indirect. For example, vagus nerve stimulation activates diverse nuclei throughout the brainstem, provoking a release of acetylcholine and norepinephrine throughout the brain that predisposes vicariously distributed circuits to increase their responses to neurorehabilitation⁸⁶ (**Fig. 2**). As with most neuromodulation therapies, the timing of the stimulation must coincide with relevant motor events to maximize recovery⁸⁷. When delivered after cervical SCI, closed-loop vagus nerve stimulation promoted the growth of neuronal projections associated with the control of hand musculature⁸⁷. Improvement of manual dexterity paralleled this anatomical reorganization, but whether and how specific neuronal populations contributed to this recovery remains unknown.

Neuromodulation of brainstem circuits

The majority of SCIs spare bridges of white matter within which mixed populations of brainstem-derived projections reside. When few projections are spared, they fail to mediate volitional muscular contractions. This understanding led to neuromodulation therapies that aim to recruit these spared projections to elicit movement. For example, the delivery of deep brain stimulation within the MLR activates reticulospinal neurons, which improved walking after SCI³⁴ (**Fig. 2**). These results are

comparable to those observed during motor cortex stimulation, suggesting that the brain fails to engage the entire population of reticulospinal neurons with spared projections below a SCI.

The relevance of this ancestral locomotor system for the recovery of walking in humans remains unclear. Moreover, this region is difficult to target surgically since the MLR is primarily defined functionally within the scattered topology of the pedunculopontine nucleus. The lack of anatomical landmarks is likely responsible for the variable outcomes when deep brain stimulation is delivered in this region to improve gait in patients with Parkinson's disease⁸⁸. However, recent studies have segregated the MLR into anatomically distinct nuclei with defined populations of projection-stratified neurons that regulate specific behaviors, beyond locomotion³⁷. These studies open the possibility that more refined targets could be identified, or even upstream regions with more circumscribed anatomical topology.

Neuromodulation of spinal circuits

Ultimately, spinal circuits generate the muscular contractions that regulate motor actions. Therefore, it is logical that tapping into these circuits would result in the generation of organized muscular activity. Indeed, classical experiments from the beginning of the past century documented the initiation of walking when the isolated spinal cord of cats and dogs was stimulated electrically⁸⁹. The same observations were made in humans during the 1980s⁹⁰. It is now well-established that delivering continuous electrical stimulation to the lumbar spinal cord using epidural^{91,92}, intraspinal⁹³ or transcutaneous⁹⁴ methods can elicit rhythmic leg movements, weight-bearing standing, and even independent stepping in animal models¹⁸ and humans with SCI^{91,92,95} (**Fig. 2**).

Pharmacological neuromodulation based on monoaminergic agents can also reactivate the spinal cord below a SCI⁹⁶, and acts synergistically with electrical neuromodulation therapies to promote movement⁵⁴. When a sufficient number of supraspinal projections are spared, these therapies even enable these otherwise silent residual projections to engage spinal circuits⁵. This mechanism, which was unmasked in preclinical models⁵, has restored volitional control over the activity of paralyzed muscles in humans^{91,92}.

These observations motivated studies that sought to dissect the mechanisms of epidural electrical stimulation (EES). It was found that EES elicits electrical currents that do not modulate neurons directly, but instead flow within the cerebrospinal fluid where they depolarize large-diameter afferent fibers⁹⁷. Due to their relatively lower impedance, these fibers are prone to depolarization, especially where they enter the spinal cord through the dorsal root entry zones^{97,98} (**Fig. 3**). Evidence suggests that alternative stimulation methods act through the same mechanisms⁹⁹. The recruitment of large-diameter afferent fibers activates motor neurons both directly and indirectly, and contributes to transforming spinal circuits from a dormant to an excitable state^{98,100}.

These experiments revealed that the biophysical properties of the spinal cord operate as functional filters that direct unspecific electrical currents toward specific neuronal subpopulations. Concretely, EES leverages large-diameter afferent fibers as spinal cord gateways to modulate motor neurons. Since large-diameter afferent fibers primarily modulate motor neurons located in the spinal segment innervated by the root wherein these afferents reside^{92,101}, targeting individual dorsal roots enables the modulation of distinct motor pool ensembles^{92,101,102}. This biological principle led to stimulation strategies¹⁰¹⁻¹⁰⁴ that target the individual dorsal root entry zones with a temporal structure aiming to reproduce the natural spatiotemporal activation pattern of motor neurons¹⁰⁵ (**Fig. 3**). These biomimetic stimulation programs can support various motor activities^{92,101,102}, since stimulation

patterns can be adjusted to match the requirements of the desired activity. Biomimetic EES programs enabled standing, walking, biking, swimming and even trunk movements in people with complete sensorimotor paralysis ¹⁰⁶.

While the lumbar spinal cord has been the primary focus of studies on EES, experiments in NHP models ¹⁰⁷ and two humans with tetraplegia ¹⁰⁸ suggested that targeting the cervical dorsal root entry zones may also restore hand dexterity. However, in the context of complex hand gestures, it may be necessary to enable the brain to control the stimulation directly. Brain-controlled regulation of EES can be achieved using brain-computer interface technologies ¹⁰².

Neurorehabilitation supported by EES improves motor performance, both with and without EES ⁹². Individuals with chronic SCI have regained volitional control over the activity of previously paralyzed muscles, and could even recover natural walking without any support nor stimulation. The mechanisms underlying this long-term recovery remain undefined in humans, but preclinical studies uncovered the extensive growth of new connections in relevant regions of the brainstem and spinal cord ^{5,18}. The topology of this growth suggested that molecular cues attract these new connections onto specific neuronal populations. However, this possibility has not been reported thus far.

The understanding that EES utilizes large-diameter afferents as gateways to circuits in the spinal cord opened the possibility to develop neuromodulation therapies that improve other neurological functions, especially autonomic functions which are ranked amongst the top priorities for people with SCI (**Box 1**).

Perspectives on neuromodulation therapies

Neuromodulation of anatomically intact circuits in the brain, brainstem, and spinal cord have shown realistic promise to improve various neurological functions after SCI. However, current approaches exclusively based on electricity are poorly specific. Even when the biophysical and/or functional properties of neural tissues steer electrical currents towards specific neuronal subpopulations, the resolution of these natural filters remains limited in regards to the highly specialized flow of communication that normally circulates in the intact nervous system. Identification of the neuronal subpopulations that are engaged and remodeled in response to electrical stimulation may open avenues for more targeted interventions that may be combined with pharmacological agents. Yet, neuromodulation therapies mediate improvements that remain incomplete, and thus not fully satisfying. Moreover, the efficacy of neuromodulation therapies correlates with the relative amount of residual supraspinal projections below the injury. Consequently, the reconstitution of circuits with biological repair strategies remains essential to maximize recovery.

Biological strategies to reconstitute circuits

The reconstitution of circuits following spinal cord damage comes in several interpretations, which each target specific mechanisms and comprise unique challenges (**Box 2**). The more accomplishable interpretation consists of densifying the projectome of neurons that retain axons below the injury. When the SCI is complete, however, reconstitution of circuits implies the regeneration of severed axons through hostile tissues to repair damaged circuits or form new **relay circuits that bypass the lesion** and restore the flow of communication across the injury. Alternatively, these hostile tissues can be repopulated with grafts that reconstitute functional spinal cord environments. Below, we briefly summarize the biological strategies that target each of these

interpretations, **with a focus on the reconstitution of circuits after SCI to adhere with the theme of this review (Fig. 4).**

Densification of projections from spared circuits

Despite noticeable anatomical-functional paradoxes ¹⁰⁹, natural recovery from SCI largely correlates with the relative amount of **spared neuronal pathways**. This trivial etiology makes it abundantly clear that augmenting recovery from an incomplete SCI will require the densification of projections from spared circuits. Neutralizing inhibitory molecules or targeting intrinsic neuronal growth competence are effective strategies to promote this remodeling (**Box 3**).

When axons are severed within the adult central nervous system, they fail to regenerate. **Extrinsic inhibitors found in degenerating myelin and astrocyte scar borders were once thought to be responsible for this failure** ⁶. This understanding launched a race to identify inhibitory molecules and develop strategies to neutralize them. The original experiments suggested that these therapies act by promoting the regeneration of severed axons across the site of injury ¹¹⁰. **However, modern methods revealed that these interventions do not promote the regeneration of corticospinal tract axons through scars, but rather mediates short-distance growth of axon collaterals over short distances in healthy tissue** ^{6,111}. Early efforts were conducted with the hope that a singular solution would be sufficient to neutralize inhibition and thus overcome regenerative failure. These hopes have declined with the realization that reducing inhibition does not promote sufficient regrowth of severed axons ^{6,111}.

In parallel, others have focused on identifying regeneration-associated genes to reactivate intrinsic growth programs of neurons ¹¹² **and stabilize growth cones** ¹¹³ (**Box 3**). Regrowth of severed axons from corticospinal, retinal, and propriospinal neurons has been achieved with the manipulation of PTEN ¹¹⁴, cytokine signalling 3 (SOCS3) ¹¹⁵, STAT3 ¹¹⁵, SOX11 ¹¹⁶, osteopontin (OPN) ^{117,118}, insulin growth factor 1 (IGF-1) ^{117,118}, ciliary neurotrophic factor (CNTF) ¹¹⁸, and Krüppel-like family (KLFs) ¹¹⁹, neuronal RhoA ¹²⁰, among others ¹²¹. Moreover, transcription and growth factors can be manipulated concurrently to augment this regrowth. Activation of mTOR and STAT3 pathways with PTEN and SOCS3 codeletion, or overexpression of the growth factors IGF-1 and OPN, induced a synergistic regrowth of axons across astrocyte bridges and into topologically relevant targets below the injury, which was sufficient to restore some function ¹¹⁷. **Transient exposure to reduced oxygen levels, called intermittent hypoxia, is an alternative strategy to modulate raphe serotonergic neurons, trigger BDNF synthesis, and thereby promote the growth of serotonergic projections below the injury** ¹²². **Likewise, neuronal activity promotes the release of various neurotrophic factors that augment the growth of spared neuronal projections. Neurorehabilitation leverages this mechanism to improve functional recovery** ⁴³.

While impressive, these circuit reconstitutions present limitations. First, the regrowth of severed axons was only obtained for axons originating from specific populations of neurons. The remarkable diversity of projection neurons in the brain, brainstem, and spinal cord suggests that unique combinations of transcription and growth factors may be necessary to induce axon regrowth from each neuronal subpopulation ^{118,123}. Second, the accessibility to active gene regulatory regions may limit the efficacy of transcription factor manipulation. Understanding spatial and temporal changes in transcriptional and chromatin environments in neuronal subpopulations could lead to the development of targeted, temporally-controlled strategies to improve chromatin accessibility and transcriptional initiation in recovery-organizing cells. Thirdly, increasing intrinsic growth competence

of neurons promotes axon repair through healthy spinal cord tissue, but stimulated axons abruptly stop when encountered with fibrotic scar tissue^{118,124}. Therefore, a formidable challenge in neural repair remains the reconstitution of damaged circuits or formation of new circuits that reestablish communication across complete SCI.

Reconstitution of damaged circuits

A complete SCI not only interrupts the communication across the injury, but also provokes the formation of fibrotic scar tissues with different lesion compartments that each present challenges to reconstitute spinal circuits (**Box 2**). Cajal posited that regrowing axons through such hostile tissues would require recapitulating the conditions that stimulate and guide the growth of axons during development¹²⁵. Many studies illustrated certain components of this hypothesis^{126–128}. **This prediction contributed to a developmentally inspired multi-pronged repair strategy that reactivated the intrinsic growth capacity of neurons, induced the formation of axon growth supportive substrates within the core lesion compartment, and guided axons downstream using spatially and temporally controlled release of growth factors**¹¹⁸. Stimulated, supported, and chemoattracted axons regrew through astrocyte scar borders, across the fibrotic scar, and into healthy tissues where they formed synaptic contacts with neurons below the complete SCI (**Fig. 4**). This strategy targeted propriospinal neurons with the assumption that these cells would become relay circuits capable of mediating recovery. Despite the **pronounced** regrowth of electrophysiologically conductive axons, no detectable recovery of function has been observed¹¹⁸. Various mechanisms may explain this lack of recovery, including the absence of activity to shape these new circuits, innervation of improper targets, poor remyelination, and even axon retraction. The respective contribution of these mechanisms remains undisclosed. Equally mysterious is whether other neuronal subpopulations located in the brain and brainstem could be similarly guided through complete SCI and to relevant targets below the injury.

Engraftment of new circuits

Undoubtedly, a cure for SCI will require reconstituting the natural topology of the central nervous system. However, demonstration that intraspinal neurons may relay sufficient information downstream to produce motor behaviors led to a more optimistic definition of the requirements for meaningful recovery after SCI.

Efforts to repopulate the hostile lesion environment with relay circuits followed. Various types of cells, including neural progenitor cells (NPCs), have been grafted into the injured spinal cord with widely different success¹²⁸ (**Fig. 4**). **Only when NPCs were harvested from homologous spinal cord tissue (caudalized), supported with growth factors, and embedded in stabilizing matrices or scaffolds, did they survive the engraftment.** NPCs matured into glial cells and neurons that filled the fibrotic tissue lesion and could propel hundreds of thousands of axons along the entire rostrocaudal extent of the rodent and primate spinal cords^{129,130}. Differentiated neurons attracted projections from various host neurons located in the brain and brainstem, thus establishing relay circuits that could restore electrophysiological connectivity across complete SCI¹²⁹.

These reconstitutions of circuits with cell grafts are remarkable. Yet, equally remarkable is the limited recovery of functions that these new circuits mediated^{129–131}. Various mechanisms may be invoked to account for this discrepancy, including the importance of activity-dependent factors, guidance of axons to relevant targets, and even the necessity to differentiate NPCs into specific

neuronal subpopulations. For example, transplantation of NPCs enriched with V2a interneurons into the injury site improves recovery of diaphragm activity¹³².

Perspectives on biological strategies to reconstitute circuits

All these interpretations on the requirements for reconstituting circuits after SCI led to considerable advances in spinal cord repair⁴³. We now understand how to densify the projections from spared neurons, regrow severed axons over long-distances, and repopulate the injured spinal cord with viable circuits. However, the resulting recovery has so far been insufficient to translate into impactful clinical applications. We surmise that directing interventions to specific neuronal subpopulations¹²¹ and guiding their regrowing axons to relevant targets may be necessary to achieve recovery. Single-cell methods are opening a path to support this shift of resolution. **Even following pronounced spinal circuit repair, however, complementary interventions may be necessary to counteract the maladaptive changes that take place in circuits located below a severe SCI, as observed following multiple sclerosis**¹³³.

Molecular choreography of recovery from spinal cord damage

The prospect of a cure for SCI is unforeseeable, but we can already forecast that current neuromodulation and biological repair therapies will not complete this long-haul quest. Throughout this review, we argued that we must operate a radical transition in the resolution of our central nervous system interrogation. Instead of focusing on vaguely defined circuits and pathways, we must establish multi-omic cartographies at single-cell resolution over the entire nervous system to map the landscape of neurons that can orchestrate the natural recovery of function after SCI—thus capturing the changing properties of *recovery-organizing* neuronal subpopulations. **These large-scale, multi-omic cartographies will also identify whether and how other cell types and epigenetic mechanisms contribute to improving or impairing recovery.**

Whole-nervous system imaging¹³⁴, single-cell technologies¹³⁵, and cell-specific interrogations¹³⁶ have established the analytical tools to catalog the molecular choreography of recovery from spinal cord damage with exquisite details. We now possess technologies to dissect the molecular signatures and growth requirements one neuron at a time, across all the neurons of the nervous system and over time scales ranging from minutes to months. The resulting space-time catalogs of recovery from SCI are poised to uncover the transcriptional programs that will support the regrowth of any neuronal subpopulation from the brain, brainstem and spinal cord. We must then harness this knowledge of *recovery-organizing* neuronal subpopulations to inform therapeutic strategies that engage and reconstitute the projections from these neurons to their meaningful targets. **We anticipate that these evidence-based repair programs will be more effective than generic approaches to regrow meaningful neuronal projections, and avoid potentially unwanted regrowth. Clinically-relevant technologies to target specific neuronal populations are now available.**

This new era will unlock the blueprints to reconstitute **the natural topology of all the relevant *recovery-organizing* neuronal populations**, with the hope that the development of a cure for SCI will then follow.

Box 1 | Neurotechnologies to improve autonomic functions

Preliminary studies in feline models and humans showed that EES applied over the sacral spinal cord could modulate spinal circuits involved in the regulation of bladder and bowel functions¹³⁷. Even more conclusive were studies targeting hemodynamic instability^{138,139}. People with cervical and upper thoracic SCI experience frequent drops of blood pressure that not only affect their quality of life but also lead to life-threatening conditions. These hemodynamic events, which are referred to as orthostatic hypotension, are due to the interruption of descending signals from brainstem vasomotor regulatory circuits¹³⁹. Consequently, the sympathetic circuits in the spinal cord no longer respond to orthostatic challenges.

Circuits embedded in the low thoracic spinal cord are enriched for sympathetic preganglionic neurons¹³⁹. Engaging these neurons recruits ganglionic neurons, which release norepinephrine to activate α_1 receptors on splanchnic blood vessels and thus provoke arterial vasoconstriction¹³⁹. Large-diameter afferent fibers recruited with EES can activate sympathetic preganglionic neurons through an intermediary glutamatergic interneuron¹³⁹ (**Fig. 3**). This mechanism enables the precise regulation of sympathetic circuits. Closed-loop control of EES targeting these circuits maintained blood pressure stability during transient, varying, and sustained orthostatic challenges in rat and NHP models, as well as in humans¹³⁹. Large clinical trials are underway to turn this strategy into a treatment for people who suffer from severe orthostatic hypotension.

Box 2 | Specific challenges in each compartment of the injured region

Damage to the spinal cord is typically inflicted by mechanical insults such as laceration or contusion. This primary injury tears axons apart and causes severe bleeding, which triggers a secondary injury response involving a cascade of cellular and molecular events such as immune cell infiltration, cell death, demyelination, and scar formation. These secondary events lead to the formation of three cellularly distinct compartments, starting from a core fibrotic scar or cavity that is surrounded by an astrocyte scar border, and spared but reactive and reorganizing neural tissue¹¹².

Fibrotic scar (core) Severe inflammation provokes the formation of the fibrotic scar, which is composed of fibroblasts, pericytes, endothelial, and inflammatory cells. While the origin of the cell types responsible for fibrotic scarring has been intensely debated^{140–142}, we know that the origin is neither neuronal or glial. Therefore, the fibrotic component of the scar must be distinguished from the glial scar. Since the fibrotic scar has been ascribed an inhibitory role, many interventions sought to ablate the cellular constituents of the fibrotic scar with the goal of decreasing the extracellular matrix^{113,143}. Partial ablations have been reported to result in decreased extracellular matrix deposition and improved behavioral outcomes, while complete ablation of the same cells resulted in larger tissue damage and worsened behavioral outcomes¹⁴³. In striking contrast, a recent study revealed that the fibrotic scar can act as a permissive scaffold that supports stimulated axons to regrow through this scar^{118,124}. Differences between these studies are likely due to the specific types of extracellular matrix that are upregulated and deposited by each intervention. Deconstructing the biology of fibrotic scarring will provide actionable pathways to manipulate the extracellular matrix in order to foster the repair of damaged circuits.

Astrocyte scar border (surrounding the core) Fibrotic scars are surrounded by a thin and densely packed border of astrocytes, termed the astrocyte scar border, which is regulated through signal transducer and activator of transcription 3 (STAT3)¹⁴⁴, and leucine zipper bearing kinase (LZK) signaling¹⁴⁵. Astrocyte scar borders are almost exclusively composed of newly proliferated and reactive astroglia^{146,147}. This border was long regarded as a physical and chemical barrier to axon growth. However, the supposedly negative properties of scar border forming astrocytes have now been dismantled. We know that they are not the principal cause of regenerative failure¹²⁴, but instead restrict the spread of inflammation into viable neural tissue^{124,146,148}. Moreover, they are not the primary producers of purportedly inhibitory CSPGs¹²⁴, but can instead support the growth of stimulated axons^{118,124}. These observations imply that scar border forming astrocytes support neural repair and that hindering astrocyte scar border formation will likely be detrimental to recovery.

Spared but reactive neural tissue (neighboring the core) Adjacent to the astrocyte scar borders lies spared but reactive neural tissue, which contains hypertrophic reactive astroglia combined with neurons forming circuits and undergoing synaptic turnover.

Box 3 | Overcoming inhibition versus reactivation of growth programs

Neutralizing inhibitory molecules or targeting intrinsic neuronal growth competence have been the main strategies to promote the anatomical remodeling of residual neuronal projections after SCI.

Neutralizing inhibitory molecules

The most established strategy involves the delivery of the enzyme chondroitinase (ChABC), which digests the glycosaminoglycan side chain of chondroitin sulfate proteoglycans (CSPGs). CSPGs are the key constituents of perineuronal nets that regulate the opening and closing of the neurogenesis critical period. Devoid of perineuronal nets, neurons become available to receive synapses from newly formed axons of residual projections. Multiple independent laboratories have demonstrated that ChABC mediates functional improvements in both rodent and NHP models^{20,149}. Activity-dependent neurorehabilitation further enhances this recovery⁴². Equally popular are strategies targeting the nogo receptor reticulon 4 (RTN4), which neutralizes myelin associated inhibition¹¹⁰. Positive outcomes in rodent and NHP models have led to a multinational clinical trial that is evaluating the efficacy of antibodies against this receptor to augment manual dexterity after incomplete SCI (<https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/NCT03935321>).

Targeting intrinsic neuronal growth competence

One of the transformative moments for neural repair came from systematic screenings in optic nerve injury models. It was found that the genetic deletion of the phosphatase and tensin homologue (PTEN) induces unprecedented regrowth of injured axons from retinal ganglion cells¹¹⁴. Suppressing this transcription factor in cortical neurons induced long-distance regrowth of corticospinal tract axons through spared astrocyte bridges following SCI¹⁵⁰. These findings revealed that reactivating intrinsic neuronal growth mechanisms enables true regeneration of severed axons that become insensitive to extrinsic inhibitors. Many discoveries followed, as summarized in the main text.

Fig. 1 | Adaptive and maladaptive reorganization of brain, brainstem and spinal circuits following SCI
 A SCI triggers functional and anatomical changes throughout the nervous system. Extensive functional and anatomical reorganization of projections from neurons located in the brain, brainstem, and spinal cord above the injury naturally occur after SCI. The topological distribution of these reorganisations is illustrated in this figure, including the alterations in cortical dynamics, and growth of new axonal projections from neurons in the brain, brainstem, and spinal cord. The profound changes that these circuits undergo can contribute to natural recovery, or instead be detrimental to neurological functions and result in neuropathic pain, autonomic dysreflexia, or spasticity. To a large extent, the severity of the SCI determines whether this reorganization is directed or undirected.

Fig. 2 | Neuromodulation of anatomically intact circuits

Neuromodulation strategies, which are primarily based on electrical stimulation methods, tap into anatomically intact circuits of the brain, brainstem, and spinal cord to improve neurological functions immediately and/or promote long-term recovery of neurological functions after SCI. When the SCI is incomplete, electrical stimulation is delivered in the brain or brainstem to re-activate circuits in the spinal cord or to reinforce the strength of connections between the brain and spinal cord. When a SCI is severe, the circuits in the spinal cord lack the source of modulation and excitation that they require to be functional. Electrical spinal cord stimulation, in particular EES, can re-activate these circuits through the modulation of large-diameter afferents. When combined with neurorehabilitation, the stimulation directs the growth of residual projections from the brain and brainstem (arrows) to neuronal populations that are activated by the stimulation. This reorganization promotes recovery of volitional movement even when the stimulation is turned off.

Fig. 3 | Mechanisms through which EES restores hemodynamics and mobility

Evidence suggests that EES elicits electrical currents that do not modulate neurons directly, but instead flow around the spinal cord within the cerebrospinal fluid where they depolarize large-diameter afferent fibers. Due to their low impedance and heavy myelin contents, these fibers are prone to depolarization, especially where they enter the spinal cord through the dorsal root entry zones. Evidence suggests that alternative stimulation methods act through the same mechanisms. The recruitment of large-diameter afferent fibers activates visceral and somatic motor neurons both directly and indirectly, and contributes to transforming spinal circuits from a dormant to a highly excitable state. Since flexor and extensor motor pools are located in different spinal segments, targeting the dorsal roots projecting to the segments wherein these motor pools reside enable the modulation of specific muscles with a timing that reproduces the natural activation of these muscles.

Fig. 4 | Biological strategies to reconstitute damaged circuits

Schematic summarizing the primary biological strategies to reconstitute circuits after SCI. The reconstitution of circuits following spinal cord damage depends on the severity of injury. For incomplete injuries, regeneration of severed axons is not required, as a sufficient number of axon projections remain intact. Densifying the projectome of neurons that retain axons below the injury can be achieved by either activating intrinsic neuronal growth competence or by digesting inhibitors associated with degenerating myelin or chondroitin sulphate proteoglycans (top). When the SCI is complete, reconstitution of circuits necessitates regrowing severed axons across injury sites to restore connectivity. This regrowth can be achieved for propriospinal neurons by deploying a multi-pronged, developmentally inspired repair strategy which sequentially upregulates intrinsic neuronal growth competence, induces supportive substrates, and provides chemoattraction (middle). Alternatively, these hostile tissues can be repopulated with the engraftment of supportive neural stem cells which receive input from key supraspinal centers and relay information across injury sites to restore connectivity (bottom).

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